

Deliverable 3.3 - Requirements for data brokering system

Tier: Technology, Node

Priority Area: Cellular and molecular research

Thematic Area (if applicable): na

Executive Summary

Data brokering plays a critical role in supporting researchers in depositing datasets, especially complex multi-omics data spanning multiple technology-specific ELIXIR Deposition Databases (EDDs). Key roles include data submitter, author, broker, consultant, and developer. Building on previous analyses, this work identifies gaps in role definitions, interoperability, and tracking of submission tools. Recommendations focus on harmonising terminology, formalising brokering services, and improving technical infrastructure. Key measures include unified authentication across repositories, pre-submission metadata previews, cross-repository sample linking, dedicated broker support channels, and machine-actionable repository requirements. Formalising brokering roles clarifies responsibilities toward both researchers and repositories, ensuring trust, scalability, and compliance.

These outcomes provide a foundation for future investments and strategic planning by ELIXIR Nodes, institutions, and EDDs. Nodes offering or planning brokering services can anticipate operational, legal, and technical challenges, while interoperability initiatives and collaboration with the broader RDM community are strengthened. Overall, this work supports a more efficient, coordinated, and sustainable ecosystem for data stewardship and brokering.

Document info

Responsible Participant	ELIXIR Belgium - VIB vzw (VIB)
Dissemination level	PU

Author List

Node	Institution	Name, surname	ORCID
BE - ... ▾	Belgium - VIB vzw (VIB)	Flora, D'Anna	0000-0003-4665-6673
BE - ... ▾	Belgium - VIB vzw (VIB)	Bert, Droesbeke	0000-0003-0522-5674
SE-S... ▾	Sweden - Uppsala University	Stephan, Nylinder	0000-0001-5199-7128
SE-S... ▾	Sweden - Stockholm University	Yvonne, Kallberg	0000-0002-3977-9600
LU-L... ▾	Luxembourg - University of Luxembourg	Vilem, Ded	0000-0001-9235-8496
NO-... ▾	Norway - University of Bergen	Korbinian, Bösl	0000-0003-0498-4273
DE-G... ▾	Germany - Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies (HITS)	Ulrike, Wittig	0000-0002-9077-5664
NL-N... ▾	Netherlands - Health-RI Foundation	Walter, Baccinelli	0000-0001-8888-4792
PT-P... ▾	Portugal - BIP4DAB Association (BioData) (Associação BIP4DAB)	Miguel, Cisneiros	0000-0002-6681-8564
LU-L... ▾	Luxembourg - University of Luxembourg	Hana, Marcetic	0000-0002-3841-0377
NO-... ▾	Norway - University of Tromsø	Åberg, Espen	0000-0002-2280-7978
SE-S... ▾	Sweden - Uppsala University	Niclas, Jareborg	0000-0002-4520-044X

Abbreviations and Acronyms

RDM	Research Data Management
EDD	ELIXIR Deposition Database
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure

Contents

Executive Summary	1
Document info	1
Author List	3
Abbreviations and Acronyms	4
Contents	5
Introduction	6
Role definitions	7
Data submitter	7
Author	7
Brokering roles	7
Broker	7
Consultant	7
Developer	7
Recommendations	8
General	8
Key suggestions	9
Broker	10
Recommendations for EDD:	10
Recommendations for broker:	11
Key suggestions	12
Consultant	12
Developer	13
Key suggestions	14
Outcomes and expected impact	15
Dissemination Plans	15

Introduction

Data brokering refers to enabling the collection, aggregation, and exchange of data from researchers and organizations, to data repositories. As research increasingly relies on complex multi-omics datasets, data brokering ensures that this information is accessible, standardized, and reusable. The aim of data brokering is to support the seamless transfer of generated data to repositories by data brokers providing tools and expert knowledge. Here we mainly focus on brokering activities targeting the repositories listed as ELIXIR Deposition Databases for Biomolecular Data (EDD)¹.

Building on the work from the ELIXIR Data Platform WP2, which analysed how repositories support data deposition, brokering, and multi-omics data linkage², this study looks at how data stewards and RDM professionals can better support researchers during data deposition. The WP2 landscape analysis showed that while most repositories recognise common roles such as data submitter and author, the terminology and responsibilities are not standardised, and distinctions between submitters, brokers, and support staff are often unclear. Tools like COPO³, ISA⁴, DataPLANT⁵, and FAIRDOME-SEEK⁶ help with depositions, but their use is rarely recorded or tracked by repositories. Support for multi-omics depositions also remains fragmented, with limited documentation and inconsistent linking of related datasets. These gaps highlight the need for clearer role definitions and responsibilities, better tracking of submission tools, and more coordinated approaches to linking data across repositories. Building on these findings, this work offers recommendations and examples of how improved support and workflows could strengthen data deposition processes and overall data flow.

To clarify terminology, the *data deposition process* can be described as progressing through these distinct stages: **registering**, where metadata are recorded without uploading data; **submitting**, which involves uploading and validating data and metadata; **depositing**, during which the data are securely stored in the repository; and **publishing**, during which the dataset is formally released and made accessible. Correspondingly, datasets can be said to reach the stages of registered, submitted,

¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17106051>

³ <https://copo-project.org/>

⁴ <https://isa-tools.org/>

⁵ <https://www.nfdi4plants.org/>

⁶ <https://fairdomseek.org/>

deposited, and published. We are aware that some of these terms are used interchangeably when referring to transferring data to data repositories.

Role definitions

Data submitter

While the term "data submitter" conceptually refers to the individual or organisation responsible for initiating and authorizing the submission of data, its practical implementation within repositories is often tightly linked to a specific **user account**—typically identified by an email address—**through which the deposition is carried out**.

Author

An author is someone who has contributed significantly to the conception, design, execution, or interpretation of a research study, has knowledge of and authority over the dataset, and is credited for their contribution to the creation of a dataset that is of relevance.

Brokering roles

Broker

An individual or organisation performing the data deposition or updates of data on behalf of the authors to repositories.

Consultant

The individual or organisation translating repository requirements and information, and conveying this to data submitters.

Developer

An individual or organisation developing and/or providing a software system and code facilitating the process of depositing data to a repository.

Recommendations

General

Greater harmonisation and alignment of role terminology across ELIXIR Deposition Databases (EDDs) would help ensure that technical responsibilities in the data submission process are clearly defined and consistent. For instance, EMDB⁷, EMPIAR⁸ and PDB⁹ already apply more granular role definitions, even though these are not currently mapped to ontology terms (see ELIXIR Deliverable Report - D2.1 Description of landscape analysis including collection of user and repository requirements¹⁰).

Individuals with specific roles could be identified by ORCID, and their affiliations could be taken from ORCID or from ROR¹¹ ID, to provide a more standardised and objective approach to attributing contributions. This would also make it easier to quantify data-related activities for KPIs, ensuring recognition for those involved in data stewardship, brokering, and submission roles.

EDDs under the same organisation would benefit from offering a unified authentication and authorisation mechanism, ensuring consistent access across all repositories. Using a shared solution, such as Life Sciences (LS) Login or ORCID-based authentication, would streamline access for users, reduce duplication of account management, and provide a more coherent experience across services.

To enhance data quality and support author oversight, repositories could provide a pre-submission preview of input metadata, and optionally linked data files, at the very early stage of the deposition process, before any record is officially registered or submitted. This pre-submission stage would allow brokers to share the draft submission with authors for review and final approval, ensuring accuracy and completeness prior to deposition.

To enable cross-repository sample linking, EDD should support a model, with an associated (graphical) interface, that allows adding BioSamples¹² IDs to each repository sample entry when available. This would facilitate interoperability and the integration of datasets from different sources.

⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb/>

⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/empiar/>

⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17106051>

¹¹ <https://ror.org/>

¹² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/>

Repositories should maintain a service status board providing real-time information on the availability of their individual services (e.g., APIs, website, FTP). Clear communication about downtime or intermittent issues helps developers and users distinguish repository-side problems from data/user/tool - related errors, improving troubleshooting and overall reliability.

Data stewards and RDM experts in brokering roles often serve as the first line of support for researchers preparing data for submission. While this improves efficiency for researchers, brokers are frequently constrained by the response times of standard repository support channels. Establishing a fast-track communication route—such as a dedicated support channel for brokers—would streamline interactions, reduce delays, and lessen the overall support burden on repositories.

In a FAIR-by-design approach, it is important to know repository requirements for metadata, data volume, licences, and related aspects upfront, typically during the creation of a data management plan. Although this information is currently stored in FAIRsharing¹³, it is manually curated, which can lead to outdated entries and places a maintenance burden on repositories responsible for keeping their records up to date. A collaborative approach in which repositories expose this information in a machine-actionable, programmatic way—and FAIRsharing updates its records automatically—would ensure accuracy while substantially reducing the manual workload for repositories.

Key suggestions

- Harmonisation of role terminology together with the associated technical capabilities and responsibilities.
- Use ORCID to identify individuals in specific roles and retrieve affiliations from ORCID or ROR IDs.
- Provide a unified login mechanism (e.g., LS Login or ORCID) to access all repositories within the same organisation.
- Provide a pre-submission preview of metadata (and optionally data files) for author review and approval.
- Support for adding BioSamples IDs to repository sample entries to enable cross-repository linking.

¹³ <https://fairsharing.org/>

- Status board for their individual services and communication about possible downtime or intermittent services.
- Provide a dedicated fast-track communication channel for brokers to interact with repository support teams.
- Expose repository requirements in a machine-actionable format to allow FAIRsharing to update records automatically and reduce repository maintenance burden.

Broker

Recommendations for **EDD**:

Brokers should not be just “power users” or an optional attribute on a depositor’s account. In the scope of ELIXIR Data Deposition (EDD) systems, brokers should play a formal and strategic role in facilitating data submission and supporting researchers. To ensure trust and sustainability, this role must be explicitly recognized and formalized across repositories.

EDD systems should establish a **clear framework for broker recognition**. The role should be formalized between the repository and the broker, using contracts or terms of services, outlining the level of support the broker will provide to their user base and the level of support the repository will provide to the broker. It should define responsibilities for brokers and EDDs, ensuring accountability and clarity of their role.

Additionally, EDDs should provide broker inclusion criteria and a basic screening process to verify that brokers are trustworthy and compliant with data standards and sustainable in their operations.

Researchers often struggle to find reliable brokering services when preparing data for deposition systems. From the perspective of EDD systems, supporting brokers is in their best interest because brokers increase adoption of EDD platforms, reduce the number of support requests to helpdesks and boost the overall number of submitted datasets.

Although brokers are responsible for increasing visibility of their service, EDD systems can create (or contribute) and maintain a complementary openly accessible catalog of recognized broker services. This catalog can be advertised on EDD platforms for maximum visibility and enable brokers to connect and collaborate, strengthening the ecosystem.

In many existing ELIXIR data deposition systems (EDD), transferring ownership or delegating submission responsibilities is cumbersome or even impossible. For example:

- **BioStudies**¹⁴: Ownership transfer requires emailing the helpdesk.
- **ENA**¹⁵: Ownership transfer is not supported.
- **EGA**¹⁶: Possible only upon special request.

This creates friction for researchers who want to collaborate or use brokering services. Brokers often help authors prepare and submit datasets to repositories, but without an easy way to grant permissions or transfer ownership, the process becomes inefficient and error-prone.

EDD systems should adopt a more flexible model similar to **EMPIAR** and **EMDB**, where the original depositor can:

- Grant privileges to other accounts (e.g., *view*, *view/edit*, *view/edit/submit*).
- Transfer submission ownership directly within the system.

This approach would make it easier for authors to appoint brokers or collaborators without relying on manual interventions or helpdesk requests.

Recommendations for **broker**:

Researchers who choose to use a brokering service must have a clear and informed **understanding** of what the service entails. Without transparency, permission handover can become risky, leading to misunderstandings about responsibilities and compliance obligations. Formal definition of brokering service should be established. Authors (as users of the service) should acknowledge a Terms of Services or a formal SOP in case of an internal brokering office. Such a document has to clarify the responsibilities of author (user) and broker and ensure compliance with applicable legislation.

Additionally, brokers should ensure the services are advertised transparently and that detailed information describing the conditions of use is available to ensure findability and trustworthiness. This ensures the permission handover is based on an informed decision, supported by clear documentation and visible service descriptions. The documentation shall contain a list of supported repositories. Additionally, the broker

¹⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/>

¹⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>

¹⁶ <https://ega-archive.org/>

must establish a dedicated channel for submitting requests to add new repositories supported. A standardized procedure should be in place to evaluate each proposed repository and determine whether it qualifies to be included in the service portfolio.

Key suggestions

For **EDDs**:

- Brokers should have a formal, strategic role in EDD systems, not just be “power users.”
- Establish contracts or Terms of Service between repositories and brokers, defining mutual responsibilities and support levels.
- Define broker inclusion criteria and implement a screening process for trustworthiness, compliance, and sustainability.
- Create and maintain an openly accessible catalog of recognized brokers, advertised on EDD platforms for visibility.
- Enable flexible permission management, including granting privileges and transferring ownership within the system.

For **brokers**:

- Provide clear, formal definitions of brokering services and require authors to acknowledge Terms of Service or SOPs.
- Ensure brokers advertise services transparently, including conditions of use and supported repositories.
- Permission handover must be based on informed decisions supported by clear documentation.
- Brokers should maintain a list of supported repositories and a process for evaluating new ones for inclusion.

Consultant

The person providing consultancy support for a submission should be able to translate and convey repository requirements and information to the data author(s) in a clear, comprehensible way, so that the author(s) understand and can act accordingly. Sometimes this support results in written guidance, available to the public, that serves as complementary information to the repositories' own guidance. Whenever this is the

situation, the repositories should be made aware and either incorporate and update their own guidance or reference it.

Consultancy support can function to offload some of the first-line support of the EDDs, and they should therefore, on their side, support and recognise this type of brokering support role.

Developer

From the perspective of developers and providers of brokering tools, it would be helpful if repositories implemented features that make metadata more machine-actionable, accessible, and interoperable. Using established ontology terms for metadata elements and controlled lists would support greater consistency and reuse across systems. To ensure that brokering tools remain aligned with current requirements, repositories could expose their metadata specifications through mechanisms such as GitHub (with version control) or a publish–subscribe (Pub/Sub) system, accompanied by a clear release schedule and versioning policy that indicates which version is supported at any given time.

Improved and well-documented APIs are needed to support seamless integration with brokering platforms. APIs should cover both metadata and data submission and allow for the programmatic release of submitted (meta)data. The end-to-end submission process should be fully automated, requiring no human intervention (e.g., no need for emailing or contacting the repository). Where submissions involve extended validation or curation steps, repositories should provide machine-actionable mechanisms—such as API endpoints—for monitoring submission progress.

To enhance usability and support the development and validation of brokering tools, repositories should provide both “dry-run” capabilities and dedicated test or demo environments. “Dry-run” functionality should allow users to locally validate submissions without transferring data, ensuring that metadata and file structures meet repository requirements before performing an actual submission. Test or demo environments, by contrast, should enable end-to-end tool validation and user training without affecting production systems. These environments should include clear documentation describing how they operate, including expectations for unique submissions and the schedule or conditions for system resets to allow repeated testing.

Repositories could include simple mechanisms to capture which submission tool was used for each dataset. This would help track tool use across communities and provide a clearer picture of the uptake and impact of a tool.

Key suggestions

- Expose metadata requirements using ontology-based terms and provide versioned, up-to-date specifications via GitHub that can be used for independent validation or a Pub/Sub mechanism.
- Provide improved, well-documented APIs that support end-to-end automated submissions—including metadata and data upload, programmatic release, and machine-actionable endpoints for monitoring validation and curation progress.
- Provide “dry-run” validation and dedicated test/demo environments with clear documentation on operation, expected unique submissions, and system reset conditions.
- Capture and record the submission tool used for each dataset.

Outcomes and expected impact

The recommendations developed in this work provide a concrete basis for guiding future investments by ELIXIR Nodes, institutions, and EDDs. By explaining the relevance of formally defining brokering roles and responsibilities, Nodes that already offer—or plan to offer—brokering services can better anticipate operational, legal, and technical challenges and begin formalising their services in a transparent and sustainable way. This formalisation will establish clearer expectations for both researchers and repositories, enabling more trusted and scalable brokering support across the network. This work can also serve as a foundation for future collaboration between EDDs and brokers within Nodes and institutions on interoperability and the machine-actionability of metadata requirements and data submission systems. Overall, it will help organisations prioritise strategic developments that enhance service readiness, foster interoperability, and build a more coordinated ecosystem for data stewardship and brokering.

Dissemination Plans

Upload to Zenodo within the ELIXIR Zenodo Community.¹⁷

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/communities/elixir>